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RUSSIAN SETTLEMENT POLICY IN WESTERN KAZAKHSTAN IN THE SECOND HALF OF THE 19TH – BEGINNING OF THE 20TH CENTURIES

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Abstract

The article is concerned with stages and patterns of resettlement movement on lands of the Western Kazakhstan from 1868 to 1917, the spatial and organizational features of the process are considered. The researcher has analyzed the evolution of the government policy concerning the lands belonged to Kazakh nomads, ways and methods of withdrawal of lands from the Kazakhs for new settlers plots, social consequences of mass resettlement to the region in question. Mass agrarian colonization was carried out in the years of Stolypin's reform. Provinces of the exit were situated in the European part of Russia that defined ethnic and confessional structure of migrants. Resettlement movement at the end of XIX – the beginning of the XX century acted as a major factor of changes in land management of Kazakhs and destruction of a traditional nomadic community. The resettlement and agrarian policy of the government led to an aggravation of social contradictions and, as a result, increased counteraction to this policy from Kazakh nomads.

Keywords: Western Kazakhstan, resettlement movement, Stolypin reforms, land seizure, Turgai-Ural resettlement region.

Introduction

In the history of Kazakhstan during the colonial period, despite the significant achievements of domestic historiography, there are still many problems that require in-depth analysis and comprehensive assessment. One of them is the problem of studying the resettlement policy in Western Kazakhstan in the late 19th – early 20th centuries. Throughout the period under review, the population of Western Kazakhstan developed not only due to internal factors, but also as a result of the powerful influence of external influences that radically changed the course of ethnodemographic and socio-cultural processes in the region. One of these factors is population migration. The modern population of Western Kazakhstan was formed as a result of a large influx of immigrants from other parts of the country, which was especially intensified as a result of Stolypin's resettlement policy. The end of the 19th – beginning of the 20th centuries is a turning point in the history of the Kazakh people. The final liquidation of national statehood led to the transformation of Kazakhstan into a colony of the Russian Empire. Massive land seizure, resettlement policy, and a sharp reduction in the food supply due to the expropriation of Kazakh pastures in favor of peasant settlers lead to a crisis in nomadic cattle breeding. The policy of resettling peasants, accompanied by the mass eviction of Kazakhs from fertile lands, led to the destruction of traditional cattle breeding. The inconsistency in the implementation of Stolypin's reform led to increased tension in the region, both among the indigenous population that suffered during the reform and among the deceived settlers. Social tension was reflected in the growth of the revolutionary situation.

Methodology

The methodological basis was formed by a systems approach, principles of historicism and objectivity with the use of chronological and structural analysis.

Main part

The resettlement policy of tsarist Russia in Kazakhstan is divided into three periods: 1. 1861 - 1880s - peasant migration was prohibited; 2. 1880s - 1906 - relocations were allowed, but not encouraged; 3. since 1906, - after the First Russian Revolution, when the resettlement movement received government support [13, p. 13].

The abolition of serfdom in 1861 created conditions for the resettlement of peasants to the eastern regions of the empire. In the 1860s, the resettlement of peasants from the central regions of Russia to Kazakhstan began. By doing so, the government sought to resolve the agrarian problem in the internal provinces of the empire. The tsarist government issued a number of laws that infringed on the interests of the sharua, one of which was the colonial-administrative reform of 1867-1868. On October 21, 1868, the "Temporary Regulations for the Administration of the Ural, Turgai, Ak-mola and Semipalatinsk Regions" were adopted. Article 210 of the "Regulations" declared the lands occupied by nomads to be state lands and provided for public use by the Kazakhs. This later served as the legal basis for the confiscation of lands. Article 239 also granted the regional authorities the right "... to allocate forest areas for use by Russian settlements and Kyrgyz communities, with or without payment" [12, pp. 337-339]. Crop failure and famine in the European provinces caused an increased flow of settlers. At the initial stage of the migration movement, land lease agreements with the local Kazakh population were widespread.

Settlers appeared on the territory of Western Kazakhstan in the 1970s. The majority were unauthorized settlers. In 1869, the Ak-Tyube fortification was founded. At the same time, several peasant families settled near the fortress. In 1886, 177 families of settlers already lived in the Aktyubinsk district [2, p.115-116].

In the Ural region, land plots were not allocated to peasants, and agricultural settlers, as so-called non-residents, settled on the lands of the Ural Cossack Army (there were 51.3 thousand of them in those years). Settlement settlements arose on the Uil and Temir rivers and on the Caspian Sea - Shipovsky settlement, Zhilaya Kosa, etc. But these were not agricultural settlements. The allocation of land to settlers began only in 1886 [2, p.162].

The second stage of resettlement differed from the first by the active participation of the state in the preparation and implementation of this campaign. The abolition of serfdom did not solve the agrarian issue, so the tsarist government, in order to ease social tensions in the country, intensified its resettlement policy.

In 1881, the "Temporary Rules on the Resettlement of Peasants to Free State Lands" were put into effect, according to which peasants received the right to resettle to the outskirts of the empire with the permission of the relevant authorities. Nevertheless, already in 1883, the resettlement of peasants to the Steppe Region was suspended and resumed in 1889. At this stage, the tsarist government sought to gradually colonize the Kazakh steppe [18, p. 204].

Pursuing the goal of giving the resettlement movement an organized character and stopping unauthorized resettlement, in 1889 the government adopted a special regulation "On the voluntary resettlement of rural inhabitants and townspeople to state lands and on the procedure for classifying persons of the said classes who resettled in the past." According to this provision, resettlement was permitted with the permission of the relevant authorities, and the areas of resettlement were specifically defined. Those who did not receive official permission were considered unauthorized settlers and were subject to forced return [13, p. 13]. Thus, the resettlement movement was legalized under strict control "from above". In 1891 and 1892, this provision extended to the Ural and Turgai regions.

It was difficult for the authorities to combat unauthorized settlers. The Ministry of Internal Affairs ordered the Turgai military governor on July 20, 1892 to stop the resettlement of peasants to new lands who could not provide evidence of settling on the new lands and who did not have permission [6, p. 119]. Nevertheless, the number of unauthorized settlers remained high and even increased, so the government had to legalize them by including them in the places of settlement [19, p. 26].

Due to the increase in the number of settlers at the beginning of the 20th century. In the territory of the Turgai region, officials began to create the so-called "million allotment" on the territory of a number of volosts in order to allocate land to land-poor peasants [5, p.64].

The first unauthorized settlement was formed in the Uralsk district in 1890 on the territory of the Dzhirenkupinskaya volost. From 1896 to 1899, about 300 families moved here. Soon, unauthorized settlement of other volosts began. By 1900, 6 resettlement settlements were formed in the Uralsk region [16, p.157-158].

In general, the settlers in the Uralsk region during these years settled in the Temir, Yanvar-Kirsanovsky, Uralsk fortifications, on the Uil, Utva, Khobda rivers and near Lake Chelkar, renting land from the Kazakhs. Some of the settlers asked for the territory along the right bank of the Ural [2, p.116].

The resettlement policy in the Mangyshlak district of the Trans-Caspian region was regulated by the "Temporary Regulations on the Administration of the Trans-Caspian Region" of 1890. In addition, on March 26, 1893, a royal decree was issued, according to which the waters of the Caspian Sea were declared state property and the existing fishing villages were expanded. Settlers in the Trans-Caspian region enjoyed benefits - temporary exemption from paying state and zemstvo fees, from military service [14, pp.383-385]. In general, there were few settlers in the Mangyshlak district and the Inner Horde of the Astrakhan province, because the lands were not suitable for agriculture, the soil was sandy, saline, and there were few rivers.

According to the results of the resettlement policy for 1870-1896. 60,867 people arrived in the Ural region, 31,459 people in Turgai, or 22.7% of the total number of those arriving in Kazakhstan [1, p. 65].

On March 25, 1891, the Steppe Regulations were adopted, in the section "Land Organization" of which the procedure for resettlement was set out (Articles 119-136). According to Article 119, it was determined that "the lands occupied by nomads, and all the accessories of these lands, including forests ... are recognized as state property." It was also stated that the lands of nomads may "turn out to be redundant" and be transferred "to the jurisdiction of the Ministry of State Property" [12, pp. 395-396].

A new stage in the development of the resettlement movement in the Steppe Region is associated with the formation of the Committee of the Siberian Railway, whose responsibilities included facilitating the settlement of territories adjacent to the road. The construction of the railway contributed to a significant increase in the number of settlers. In order to provide for the peasants who arrived in Kazakhstan, the government needed to create a resettlement land fund. Therefore, the Committee of the Siberian Railway raised the issue of the need for a comprehensive survey of the territory of the steppe regions in order to identify surplus land and add it to the resettlement fund.

On July 13, 1893, the "Temporary Rules for the Formation of Resettlement and Reserve Plots" were approved. Based on these "Rules", the work of special parties to form resettlement plots was carried out, which were extended from 1898 to the Turgai region, and from 1904 to the Ural region.

In December 1896, the Resettlement Directorate was established as part of the Ministry of Internal Affairs. It was engaged in issuing permits for resettlement, supervised the movement and placement of settlers, and also made attempts to improve migration legislation [18, p. 204]. At the Special Conference convened in 1895, the "Program of statistical and economic survey of land use and economy of the non-Russian nomadic population of Asian Russia" was approved. Thus, for

the first time, the general grounds for setting up the research were approved, the results of which were published in the collection "Materials on Kyrgyz land use, collected and developed by the expedition to study the steppe regions". The survey of the land fund of Kazakhstan began under the leadership of statistician F.A. Shcherbina. He headed a special expedition to study the steppe regions. The work of this expedition began in 1896 and continued until 1901. The expedition surveyed 171,200 Kazakh and 8,475 Russian farms in 12 districts of the Akmola, Semipalatinsk and Turgai regions [9, p. 150]. The main task set before the researchers was to clarify the historical and economic conditions of the region in order to determine land use standards and identify surplus land in use by the Kazakh nomadic aul. To characterize Kazakh farms, Shcherbina's expedition chose the number of horses in them as the defining economic feature. According to this, the F. A. Shcherbina expedition takes a farm of 24 units of livestock, translated into horses over 2 years old, as the basis for accounting for land standards and calculating the lands necessary to ensure the economic life of a nomadic cattle breeder [9, p. 151]. This work was based on the idea of the irrationality of using the vast steppe expanses by nomads, the low profitability of the nomadic economy and the archaic way of life of the Kazakhs. Depending on the conditions of a particular district, the norms for a Kazakh farm varied from 18 to 24 units of livestock and from 5 to 8 dessiatines of annual pasture for each unit of livestock, which amounted to 90-192 dessiatines of land per household and increased surcharges of 25%. For the Aktobe district, the expedition set the norm at 18 heads of livestock and 36-168 dessiatines per farm [11, pp. 47, 54, 56].

During the survey of the Aktobe district, the expedition came to the following conclusion: "... of the total area of 5,183,623 dessiatines of land in use by the Kyrgyz, they are entitled to, according to the norms established above, 2,626,701 dessiatines of land. and, after deducting this amount from the available land, a remainder of 2,556,922 dessiatines is formed, which constitutes the surplus" [11, p. 56-57]. With the establishment of this land norm in the surveyed counties for 106 thousand Kazakh households, it is assumed it was necessary to leave 17 million dessiatines of land, and the resulting "surplus" – more than 18 million – to transfer to the resettlement fund.

By the beginning of the 20th century, there were already several main areas of peasant resettlement in Western Kazakhstan: the territory of the Aktobe district of the Turgai region, as well as the Uralsk, Lbishchensky and partially Temir districts of the Uralsk region [4, p. 55]. If earlier the government facilitated the resettlement mainly of middle-income families, then from the beginning of the 20th century the right to resettlement was received by all those wishing, regardless of their property status.

On June 25, 1903, the "Rules on benefits from the government to those resettling in Siberia (except for the Altai District) and the Steppe General Governorate" were approved. According to them, it was allowed to issue "travel loans" to families of settlers in the amount

of no more than 50 rubles and for economic arrangements – up to 100 rubles. for a period of 5 years of preferential treatment and free release of timber for construction. On June 6, 1904, a new law on the resettlement of rural inhabitants was issued, in the part concerning loans, repeating the rules of 1903 [3, p. 36]. If before 1904, resettlement was mainly unauthorized, then with the publication of the new resettlement law, it was officially recognized as one of the ways to improve the life of the land-poor population of the interior provinces [8, p. 19]. The publication of this law necessitated the allocation of new colonial funds. In 1904-1906, the tsarist government divided the territory of Kazakhstan into four resettlement regions: Turgai-Ural, Akmola, Semipalatinsk and Syr Darya. The law on the formation of resettlement areas in the Ural region was issued on April 12, 1904, and in the Turgai region - on January 2, 1906 [8, p.32]. The resettlement departments that were formed in each region were charged with the responsibility of identifying new "surplus" lands to create a "resettlement fund".

From 1893 to 1905, 4,074,180 dessiatines of land were seized in the steppe regions, of which 1,024,412 dessiatines were in the Turgai-Ural region [7, p.170].

The aggravation of the agrarian issue during the revolutionary events of 1905-1907 led to the apogee of the colonial-conquering land policy. Mass agrarian colonization of the territory of Kazakhstan was carried out during the years of the Stolypin reform, the purpose of which was to eliminate peasant landlessness in Russia and smooth out the revolutionary movement by mass resettlement of the poorest strata of the peasantry to the east.

A new course of resettlement policy began. Chairman of the Council of Ministers and Minister of Internal Affairs in 1906-1911 P.A. Stolypin developed the principles of modernization of the empire, the first condition of which was to make the peasant the owner of the land. According to the Stolypin reforms, peasants were allowed to leave the community with their allotment and organize farms. However, while maintaining landownership, the question of new lands for the peasants arises.

The results of F. Shcherbina's expedition no longer satisfy the government. The question of revising the norms of Kazakh land use towards their reduction and the need for a new expeditionary survey is raised. As early as March 1905, a conference was convened in St. Petersburg on the formation of resettlement areas in the Steppe Regions. The conference decided to grant workers of land allocation parties the right to reduce the land provision standards for Kazakhs established by F. Shcherbina's expedition.

In 1907, Stolypin convened a special interdepartmental conference on land management for Kazakhs. The conference received petitions from Kazakhs asking for land management for the indigenous population of the region, which itself was already suffering from a shortage of land in many areas. The conference decided that land management for Kazakhs could not be allowed at the present time, since this would have an unfavorable effect on the size of the colonization fund [8, p.30-34].

The conference eventually came to the conclusion that the confiscation of wintering areas and the demolition of buildings from them was a legal action [8, p.59]. The land provision standards established by Shcherbina's expedition, in the opinion of the meeting, were outdated, therefore new, reduced standards had to be established.

In this regard, it was necessary to send new expeditions that could substantiate the need for a sharp reduction in land standards. During 1906-1914, the Resettlement Administration, with the help of 19 expeditionary detachments, surveyed approximately 40 million dessiatines of land. Over 16 million dessiatines were recognized as suitable for cultural development.

In 1904-1912, under the leadership of P.P. Khvorostansky, statistical studies were conducted in several districts of Western Kazakhstan: Irgiz, Ural, Temir, Aktyubinsk. In the Ural region, 929,132 dessiatines of "surplus" were determined, in the Turgai region 1,682,357 dessiatines [15, p. 261]. These expeditions developed new reduced land norms. Now they were reduced to the area necessary to maintain 16 units of livestock per horse. For example, land use norms in the Aktyubinsk district were reduced from 123 dessiatines to 27 dessiatines – by 4 times.

Soon, the calculations of new expeditions seemed insufficient to the government. Already in 1908, as the demands of the Resettlement Administration increased, the government made greater efforts to transfer the Kazakhs to a settled way of life. In February 1909, a meeting of the commission of the State Inspectorate for Land Reclamation and the Resettlement Administration was held. At the meeting, the draft of the Resettlement Administration on the procedure for land allocation work in the Steppe Region was discussed. It was decided to provide the Kazakhs with plots of land no more than 15 dessiatines per capita. This conclusion was used as the basis for the new "Instruction on the procedure for determining the state land fund in the Ak-mola, Semipalatinsk, Turgai and Ural regions for resettlement, as well as other state needs" and was approved by the Council of Ministers on June 9, 1909. In accordance with the instruction, the practice of confiscating land in excess of the 15-dessiatine norm from Kazakhs engaged in agriculture is carried out [10, pp. 157-158]. The instruction also legalized the practice of demolishing buildings during the confiscation of land.

The resettlement department sought to select primarily arable land for the colonization fund. The confiscation of water sources also had very serious consequences. Forests were also withdrawn from the use of the local population.

In the Turgai region, Aktobe district was mainly populated. 15 villages were created here. In total, 112.5 thousand people moved to Aktobe and Irgiz districts from 1897 to 1915, of which 110.1 thousand moved to Aktobe district. In the entire West Kazakhstan region, the highest proportion of settlers was recorded here - they made up 45.4% of the total population of this district [16, p. 159]. In another part of the region, in the Uralsk region, the preparation of resettlement areas was completed by 1903. From this moment on, the period of the most active settlement began. The division of resettlement areas began with the Uralsk and Temirsk districts. In 1906-1910, 47,018 people were settled here, for whom 102 land plots with a total area of over 638 thousand dessiatines were allocated. Of the total number of settlers, 40,211 people (85.5%) settled in the Uralsk district, 8,366 people (17.7%) in the Temirsk district, and 2,225 people (4.7%) in the Gurevsky district. There were no settlers in the Lbishchensk district, but the number of non-residents increased sharply here, which is explained by the resettlement of those who arrived on the territory of the Cossack lands [16, p. 160]. In 1910-1915. In the Uralsk district, over 38 thousand people moved. In the Mangyshlak district of the Transcaspian region, the settlers settled the coastal fishing areas. The fishing villages of Nikolaevsky (1847), Dolgy (1876), and Zavorot (1892) were founded in this region. By 1910, a total of 1,615 people lived in just 3 villages [14, p. 353, 369, 388]. From 1906 to 1915, 580,587 male souls arrived in the resettlement areas of the Steppe Territory. Of these, 221,119 people (38%) were sent to the Turgay-Uralsk resettlement region.

The most intensive period of resettlement occurred in 1906-1911. If we trace the dynamics of the number of migrants by year, we see that the very first year after the issuance of the decree of 1906 gave a huge surge. The peak of migration occurred in 1907 – 46,209 men arrived. The level of migration decreases and increases in waves, and by 1915 it falls to 6,746 souls (table 1).

Table 1.

Migration to the Turgay-Ural resettlement region, 1906-1915

Years	Arrived		
	Ural and Turgay regions		Total to Kazakhstan
	Abs.	%	
1906	6 000	23,9	25 100
1907	46 209	57,5	80 360
1908	16 337	20,4	80 157
1909	29 234	33,3	87 711
1910	33 696	50,2	67 097
1911	32 158	43,5	73 994
1912	12 937	31,5	41 077
1913	18 631	37,5	50 291
1914	19 160	35,9	53 360
1915	6 746	31,5	21 440
Total:	221 108	38,1	580 587

[17, pp. 144-145]

The reduction in the number of settlers illustrates the unsuccessful outcome of the reform. This is also indicated by the significant outflow of settlers. Thus, from 20 to 34% of settlers in 1906-1915 returned back annually.

In total, 335,292 settlers of both sexes settled in the Turgai and Ural regions from 1870 to 1914 [1, p.70].

The population of the Turgai and Ural regions by 1914 compared to 1870 increased almost 2 times, from 807,599 to 1,530,032 people. This was due to the large influx of settlers [1, p.78].

The share of Kazakhs was rapidly decreasing, mainly due to migration from European Russia. The share of Kazakhs in the Turgai region fell by 31.04%, in the Ural region by 15.73% [2, p. 178]. At the same time, an increase in the number of Kazakhs was noted in the Gurevsky district by 177%, in Temir by 155%, in Bukeyevsky by 159% and in Mangyshlak by 113%. The increase in the number of Kazakhs in the more southern districts occurred as a result of their outflow from the Uralsky and Lbischensky districts [16, pp. 160-161]. By 1915, the size of the confiscated land areas in all of pre-revolutionary Kazakhstan amounted to 21,206,187 dessiatines, of which 5,402,458 dessiatines were in the Turgai-Ural resettlement region [19, p.61]. In addition, lands for Cossack troops, for forest dachas and other state needs, for the location of cities and railways were excluded from the land use of the Kazakhs. The total volume of confiscated lands was estimated with the resettlement fund amounted to more than 45 million dess.

Nevertheless, by 1917 there were still 112,000 unoccupied per capita shares. These plots were not occupied due to the fact that a significant part of them were not provided with water and were generally unsuitable for settlement. In the end, the official bodies recognized that the resettlement did not play the role that was assigned to it. The Commission on Resettlement and Colonization in August-September 1917 came to the conclusion that the resettlement policy had reached a dead end. It was proposed to replace the term "resettlement" with the term "colonization".

Findings

Thus, by the end of the 19th century, Kazakhstan had become a colony of the Russian Empire. At the beginning of the 20th century, Kazakhstan experienced a radical transformation of ethnic processes caused by the intensification of the migration movement. As a result, the ratio of the numbers of different ethnic groups inhabiting Kazakhstan changed. In particular, the proportion of the Russian-Ukrainian population increased significantly. At the beginning of the 20th century, Kazakhstan, as well as other national outskirts that experienced colonial oppression, experienced a crisis situation. The arbitrariness of the Russian military-police system of governance, the declaration of the territory of Kazakhstan as state property of the Russian Empire, the violent displacement of the Kazakh population from fertile lands, the stagnation of the traditional cattle-breeding economy of the Kazakhs and the cultural development of the Kazakh people, were manifestations of the crisis situation.

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